

LOAD-DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

WITH INTEGRALLY-FORMED BRAIDED AND WITH MACHINED CIRCULAR HOLES

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Abstract

From a strength-to-weight point of view, fibrous composites appear to be superior to other current structural materials, such as metal alloys. However, composite materials have less ability to absorb stress concentrations around holes and cut-outs, which are commonly adopted in structure attachments. The present work investigates a technique to increase the bearing strength of attachment holes using braiding process. Braiding is an established textile process for weaving a tubular fabric. In operation, the fiber tows from the moving and stationary carriers are braided on a mandrel feeding through the center of the machine at a controlled rate and shed angle, as shown in Fig. 1. The structural performance of braided and machined holes (Fig. 2) has been compared in this study. All specimens were made of ± 45 -deg. graphite/epoxy without axial yarns.

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Four 0.5 inch diameter aluminum pins were machined to a cone shape and were inserted into selected holes (0.25 in. dia.) on mandrel, to guide and deposit the yarns around pins (Figs. 3 and 4). The finished cylinders consist of three braided layers and 0.066 inch wall thickness. The cured cylinder was then slipped off the mandrel (Fig. 5) and cut into different specimen lengths. There were four types of specimens (Fig. 6): 6-inch long with braided holes (Type 1), and with machined holes (Type 2); 4-inch long with braided holes (Type 3), and with machined holes (Type 4).

The ends of the Types 1 and 2 cylinder were held in tapered metal grips with an epoxy potting material to reduce the grip transitional stresses (Fig. 7). The specimens were first tested in the elastic range under both axial tension or compression, while the central holes either open (open hole) or having a neat-fitting steel pin inserted (rigid hole). The open hole tubes were then tested in tension to failure, A pin-joint

fixture was designed to transfer load through a neat-fit steel pin to the Types 3 and 4 cylinders (Fig. 8). Both the circumferential strains around the circular hole and the axial strains along the cylinder length and circumference were measured (Fig. 6). Figs. 9 and 10 are the typical load-displacement curves. In Tables 1 and 2, the circumferential strains, ϵ_{θ} , are normalized by the far field strain for the 6 inch and 4 inch tubular specimens, respectively.

Under tension loading, a necking phenomenon was observed at the midlength of the cylinder (Fig. 11). Most of the specimens failed in a shear mode, as shown in Figs. 12 and 13. Failure loads are listed in Table 3.

As listed in Table 4, a significant improvement of the joint bearing strength of the composite material resulted from the braided hole concept. Failure modes can be seen in Fig. 14. The same bearing strength ratio was obtained for braided and machined holes on the multi-pin-loaded hole cylinders (Fig. 15).

Table 1
 $\epsilon_{\theta} / \bar{\epsilon}$ Distribution Around the Circular Hole

Axial Loading		Tension			Compression		
θ^{**} (deg)		0	45	90	0	45	90
Braided Hole	Open Hole	(-)0.23 ⁺	(-)0.17	(+)0.34	(+)0.21	(+)0.18	(-)0.38
	Rigid Hole	(-)0.18	(-)0.01	(+)0.36	(+)0.21	(+)0.11	(-)0.39
Machined Hole	Open Hole	(-)0.57	(+)1.01	(+)2.26	(+)0.82	(-)0.97	(-)2.33
	Rigid Hole	(-)1.00	(+)0.83	(+)1.53	(+)1.02	(-)0.87	(-)1.42

* $\bar{\epsilon}$: Average strain at $\bar{r} = 1.5$ in.

** θ : Angle between the loading direction and the position of strain gage.

⁺(+): tension; (-): compression.

Table 2
 $\epsilon_{\theta} / \bar{\epsilon}$ Distribution Around the Circular Hole

Pin Loading	Tension			Compression		
θ	0	45	90	0	45	90
Braided Hole	(+) 2.75	(+)3.41	(+)4.96	(-)0.11	(+)0.35	(+)2.46
Machined Hole	(-)16.91	(+)8.14	(+)8.19	(+)0.02	(+)0.04	(+)1.85

Table 3
Tension Failure Loads of Braided Cylinders with Open Hole

Specimen No.	Braided Hole	Machined Hole
1	15,000 lbs	8,600 lbs
2	12,500 lbs	11,650 lbs
3	14,700 lbs	14,000 lbs

Table 4
Failure Loads of Braided Cylinders with Pin-Loaded Holes

Specimen No.	Braided Hole	Machined Hole
1	2,000 lbs	1,100 lbs (1,010) ⁺
2	2,325 lbs	1,080 lbs (990)
3	2,090 lbs	1,440 lbs (1,450)
Avg.	2,140 lbs	1,210 lbs (1,140)

+ () is the first peak load.

Fig. 1 A 144-Carrier Triaxial Textile Braider

(a) Braided Hole

(b) Machined Hole

Fig. 2 Braided and Machined Holes

Fig. 3 Braiding Process of Composite Cylinder with Braided Holes

Fig. 4 Guide Pin for Braiding Hole on Braided Cylinder

Fig. 5 Braided Cylinder, Metal Mandrel and Pins

Fig. 6 Experimental Specimens

Fig. 7 Tubular Specimen Grip Configuration [8]

Fig. 8 Mechanical Pin Joint Test

Fig. 9 Cylinders with Open Holes in Tension

Fig. 10 Cylinders with Pin-Loaded Holes in Tension

Fig. 11 Necking Phenomenon in Tension

Fig. 12 Cylinder Failed in Shear Mode

(a) Type 1 Specimen (Braided Holes)

(b) Type 2 Specimen (Machined Holes)

Fig. 13 Tensile Failure Specimens

(a) Type 3 Specimen (Braided Holes)

(b) Type 4 Specimen (Machined Holes)

Fig. 14 Pin-Loaded Failure Specimens

(a) 12 inch Long Multi-Hole Specimens: Machined Holes (top) and Braided Holes (bottom)

(b) Pin-Loaded Specimen in Tension

Fig. 15 Two-Pin Cylinders and Test Setup